

PERSONAL PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS IN LEADERSHIP AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF THE LEADER

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Abstract. *This article is about the personal psychological characteristics and psychological health of the leader. Physical health and mental health are very necessary for the leader to get his place. The reason is that in the process of socialization in society, a person's psychological health, the ability to establish interpersonal relationships, altruism, and empathic ability are considered necessary elements in the process of socialization. The personal psychological characteristics and psychological health of the leader are of great importance in the interpersonal relationship and the interaction between the manager and the employee.*

Keywords: *socialization, leader, altruism, empathic ability, cognitive, mental-emotional, character, social institutions, faith.*

Introduction. There is a long-standing ability in society, and people have always occupied different categories. Someone's activities are related to management someone else is considered to perform these tasks. Therefore, today we want to dwell on the activities of leadership and its essence, understanding and psychological health of the leader. In leadership activities, his psychological health is considered an important factor, which directly depends on the social background of the leader, the upbringing he received in the family, personal psychological characteristics and of course also on the employees.

The study of the problem of managerial personnel occupies a significant place in the history of psychology. The main reason for this is sociology, the role of the leader in social life in the historical ethos of Social Psychology, mamlaka, his poverty in the fate of the people, progress prosperity, happy marriage are explained in many ways depending on his personality, activity, abilities, intelligence. In the teachings of our thinker ancestors, in folk art, there is an excess of information about the just and unjust king. In the works of Abu Rayhan Beruniy, Al-Farabi's manuscripts, instructive opinions were expressed on the personal qualities of the leader (referring to the holders of high positions), the complex, responsible tasks that stand before them, the instructions for the prevention and elimination of certain vices. In particular, the leader's understanding, wisdom, truthfulness, popularism, dishonesty, generosity were emphasized on the basis of scientific and practical examples.

Let us dwell on the ideological and political qualities of the personality of the leader
ideological-political belief, self-sacrifice, principalities, political literacy, social fao-llik, social duty awareness, social thinking, organization, entrepreneurship;

- professional-specialized qualities; professional maturity, independence, erudition, criticality of intelligence, analysis of information, ability to express one's opinion, predisposition to research;

- emotional and moral qualities: patriotism, exactingness, humility, respect for others, self-confidence, honesty, fairness, impartiality, culture and etiquette of behavior, rational assessment, self-perfection, modernity, adherence to moral rules.

- special abilities; faith-faithfulness, organization, oratory and authoritative abilities, sensitivity, attitude adjustment, focus, accuracy, impartiality;

-these are the individual differences in organization: psychological, selectivity, practical intelligence, criticality, organization, ideological and political qualities of the person of the head of will.

A high effect cannot be achieved without special training of leaders. To do this, it is advisable, first of all, to apply trainings that form life skills, enter into a communicative, interpersonal relationship, motivate decisions, solve the problem, maintain a healthy lifestyle, develop abilities and direct them, promote human perfection.

In leadership, management culture stewardship is a social role, consisting of a limited, conceivable form of behavior, which is expected from an individual who occupies a specific position in the system of social and interpersonal relations. The description of the social role also includes the value and character, social Masters, beliefs and feelings, goals and desires, from which a ratio is given to a person occupying a special status in society, which is expected from him.

One of the most important adjectives in the social role description above is the ones that are expected of the administrator, from which it is hoped. Waiting from the controller, hoping for it is such a psychological state that it reflects the occurrence of a specific event, the probability of manifestation of an important property of some object. Expectation it is not only imagination, but also an inner ustanovka, which means the extents of the individual.

Studies conducted show that employees rated such qualities as ideological beliefs, honesty, fairness objectivity, performance in leaders in the first place, initiative, demanding, resourcefulness, creating a creative atmosphere in the team, identifying and disseminating progressive experience, clearly forming their own requirements, rationalizing, creating a healthy social mind in the team, solving economic issues in the second place, perseverance and self-confidence, Of the listed qualities, the quality that is most important in the context of market relations is the culture of management. Because in modern enterprises, the social psychological factor rises to high positions.

Management psychology will be able to organize, organize, and tambourine interpersonal relationships, based on materials collected in the field of treatment psychology. The structure of relations, its components, the direct basis of each content on a particular system, their mutual harmonization, the ways of use of types of communication in practice have a positive effect on management activities with their applied nature. Communicative composition of relations i.e. communication, interpersonal relations. Communicative actions consist of acts, regulatory, informative functions; types such as excitatory (belief, influence, command, please), the use of which, depending on the situation, generates a warm psychological environment. As a result, some disputes are obtained.

Personal development and psychological health mental and psychological health problems are currently actively studied in local Sciences. Psychology makes an important contribution to solving these problems, primarily in connection with the development of the psychological education service. The term "psychological health" refers to this concept, in his opinion, the connection with the phenomenon of mental health I.V. Dubrovina scored. According to dubrovina,

psychological health is part of mental health, it refers to the "personality" as a whole and is determined by the "highest manifestations of the human soul." It was noted that pollen asthma was reported as the cause of asthma. Participants were also informed that the causes of mental disorders could change depending on how quickly they accelerated the disorder, and that they should quickly put their own causes and longer ones on their list. This guideline aims to identify the underlying causes of diseases, as well as direct causes that affect behavior. Finally, participants were instructed to assess how important or strong they were, each on a scale of 1 to 10, after listing the reasons. If we turn to the historical side of the emergence of ideas about psychological wellness, then they begin to form for the first time in the East. In ancient India, the 6th century BC Vedas form the Basic Rules of a healthy lifestyle. One of them is to achieve a stable balance of the psyche. The first and necessary condition for achieving this balance is complete inner freedom, the absence of a person's strict dependence on physical and mental environmental factors. Another path that led to the establishment of inner balance was the path of heart, love. The love that gives freedom is understood in bhakti yoga as the highest expression of the essence of being, not to love a person, a group of people, but love for all living beings in this world. The third way to achieve inner freedom - the mind, the path of reason - proposed jana-yoga, in which not a single yogi should give up knowledge, since it increases vitality. Using the example of asthma, participants were told that if you consider" smoking cigarettes at a young age "to be a weak factor, this indicator can be estimated up to 2 times, and if it plays a stronger role in terms of" stress". asthma can be assessed as. After evaluating the significance of the causality list and disorder, the participants became familiar with their causes and completed three tasks related to the assessment of causes. They said they would now complete three separate assignments, asking for an assessment of biological, psychological, and environmental-related causes. Participants were asked to separate each task individually, not remembering the grades given in previous tasks, and were reminded that the exact cause could be psychological, biological and environmental, as they are not mutually exclusive areas. In Eastern philosophy, special attention has always been paid to the unity of the human mind and body. So, Chinese thinkers believed that an imbalance of the body occurs as a result of mental neglect. They distinguished five painful moods: anger and anger, experience, anxiety and despair, sadness and sadness, fear and anxiety. The tendency to such moods, shortening a person's life, disrupts and paralyzes the energy of both organs and the whole organism as a whole. Joy gives the body's energy flows harmonious elasticity and prolongs life. The scope and guidelines of the tasks associated with the assessment of the causes were the same in the work. The order of the three tasks related to the evaluation of the causes was balanced using the design of the Latin square so that in the nine irregularities each task looked the same in each item of the order. The correlation between psychological, environmental and biological causes at the end of the study, clinicians supplemented the demographic data requested. In particular, the biological cause was considered less psychological and vice versa. Almost all participants showed a significant negative correlation between biological and psychological assessment of the causes. There are no clear differences between social workers, psychologists and psychiatrists on these forms. We also conducted analyzes using average biological, environmental and psychological assessments for each disorder. In Tibetan medicine, ignorance was considered a common cause of all diseases in the famous treatise "Zhud-shi". Ignorance causes a sick lifestyle, eternal dissatisfaction, leads to painful, pessimistic feelings, destructive passions, unfair anger, dissatisfaction of people. Coming to the norm in everything, overcoming natural naturalness and ignorance is the main component of a

healthy lifestyle that determines a person's physical and mental well-being. In addition, we conducted similar analyzes, taking into account the importance of the ratings that the participants gave for each reason. That is, we increased the importance of each cause, taking into account the biological, psychological and environmental point of view, and later the clinician increased its average value for all the reasons that indicated the disorder. Then we took the average from 63 doctors for each of the nine diseases. To study how these laws arose, we examined the composition of the causes that clinicians consider biological, psychological and environmental. To get an understanding of the distribution of types of causes, we classified causes as "biological" if they are rated higher than 4 on a seven-point scale to assess biological bases, if they are rated higher than the middle "psychological". psychological dimension, and for similar environmental reasons. Thus, causes can be classified as biological, purely psychological, purely ecological, or any of the three combinations. Eastern philosophy is based on the concept that inextricably connects a person with a holistic environment, nature, space, and is aimed at health, determining the possibilities of a person to resist diseases. There is also information about the psychological health of man in ancient philosophy. Thinkers of ancient times try to distinguish specific elements in this phenomenon. For example, in the treatise "on a healthy lifestyle", Hippocrates considers this phenomenon as a harmony that must be sought in compliance with a number of preventive measures. It focuses mainly on the physical health of a person. Democritus describes a spiritual spirit, the "good state of mind", in which the soul is calm and balanced, without any concern for passions, fears or other experiences. More than a third of the causes of mental disorders have been considered both psychologically and environmentally. Among the next most popular are 7% pure biological reasons, then pure psychological reasons 2%, pure environmental reasons - 7%. For illustrative purposes, we have divided the causes of clinicians into 18 categories with their biological, psychological or environmental classifications, which are indicated according to the above scheme. Often the categories of causes are "stressful life events" and "social factors", accounting for one-third of the causes listed in the list of nine mental disorders. These important causes were treated as psychological and environmental rather than biological ones.

According to the results of research in the field of psychology, we can see that the psychological health of individuals is closely related to social relations that is, interpersonal relations.

I.I.Brexman argues that health is not the absence of diseases, but the physical, social and psychological harmony of a person, friendly relations with other people, with nature and himself. According to him, "human health is the ability to maintain age-appropriate stability in the context of a sharp change in quantitative and qualitative indicators of three sources of sensory, verbal and structural information." Understanding health as a state of equilibrium, the balance between a person's ability to adapt (health potential) and constantly changing environmental conditions can be found in academic V.P.Petlenko (1997) proposed.

I.I.I. in understanding the relationship between the phenomena of "mental health" and "mental health" of dubrovina.I.Khukhlaeva thus includes the second phenomenon in the first, namely the psychological - pedagogical and socio - psychological state. health aspects-in its medical and psychological "circle". In our opinion, such a review is not legal. Considering the levels of mental health of the central concept (upper - creative, middle - flexible, lower - harmful or assimilative-adaptive), which is the characteristic of "adaptation" in the definition (according to

Xuxlaeva), it does not go beyond the very first, traditional approach - biomedical., as well as an early psychological approach to the study of human adaptation, is important.

It is worth noting that by the 21st century, health psychology is focusing more on social psychological factors, the personality itself, the self-like people who surround it, interaction between them in ensuring the stability of individual health. For example, because one of such social psychological factors, the family and the environment in it, the interactions of the founders of the family and related skills, in our conditions, in addition to the family, our relations with close relatives, neighbors also play a huge role in this, the influence of this factor should not be forgotten at some point. Therefore, when we say the socio-psychological criteria of health, we first mean the positive and sometimes negative effects that we, ourselves, others, loved ones around us, people who are important to us, our relationships to friends, colleagues, partners in labor and study activities can have on us, our health .

When it comes to mental and psychological factors of health, first of all, its features in the human personality and its holistic way of unity are implied. The solution of any achievements or problems to be achieved in this place allows, first of all, to find the answer to the question of what the “healthy person” himself is. Famous Russian psychiatrist S.S.Korsakov wrote that the more balanced, interdependent, balanced and resistant to its threatening factors from the external environment, the more energetic and healthy all the traits and characteristics associated with a healthy personality are.

It is a little difficult to move from purely psychological factors to social ones, to sharply distinguish them from each other, to put some kind of boundaries between them. Because the psychological characteristics of a person are very dependent on the system of social relations that surrounds him. At this stage, a person is perceived as a product of social relations, a social being. Therefore, at this stage, the criterion for the health of an individual is the social environment that surrounds him.

As we noted above, social factors affecting the health of a person can be attributed to the family first of all, it implies a healthy environment, family members ' understanding of each other, support for each other in each case, warmth in parent-child relationships, sincerity, in addition, established treatment greetings with friends and close relatives, dialogues at work, during rest, involvement of a person in one While some of the social factors have a positive effect on the health of the individual, others – on the contrary, can have a negative effect. Only people who feel healthy and healthy from a social and psychological point of view are active members of society, and their daily work, doing the fists, can be effective. Therefore, defects in upbringing and the effects of an inappropriate social environment can cause a person to manifest templates of misbehavior in society, and even lead to the fact that he performs criminal actions, wrong, inappropriate, absurd. When a person's attitude towards people, labor or the community is disrupted, people begin to notice his increasingly wrong and inappropriate actions, even as a person, “got strange?”, "is it okay to walk?" may arise. That is, the constant, constant activity of a person, the presence of an active life position, in combination with increasing his confidence in life, increases his resistance to various influences, sets himself good, promising goals, plans, goals and is fixed on the way to achieving it, which ultimately ensures that his health is also strong, resistant to various influences.

Therefore, a positive, sincere relationship with the environment, with people, can strengthen the individual's immunity to health. That is why ensuring the Social stage of a person's mental health requires society, people themselves to abandon superstitions, traditions that

negatively affect their psyche in time, maintain good ones, eliminate compromises in educational and educational processes, constantly increase professional qualifications, organize proper nutrition, rational rest.

The question of the criteria for assessing a healthy lifestyle, how much it has become a component of the daily life of a person is a matter of practical importance. Because an athlete can run every day, regularly carry out one or another type of exercise and, thanks to this, have achieved certain achievements in the direction of his choice, but even so, some athletes can also stand in the hospital on a permanent list for one or another chronic disease. Or there is also not enough reason to say unhealthy those who cannot make daily exercise a habit. So it is appropriate to think about what are the basics, criteria for assessing health. The psychological health of the personality of the leader is important, the reason is that the mental health of individuals operating in a leadership position in society ensures the effectiveness of labor activity, the establishment of a warm relationship with subordinates, the ability to resolve interpersonal conflicts in a distrustful way.

Conclusion. For management, the interaxial and perceptual content of circulation is important, serving to organize purposeful cooperation between the leader and subordinates, that is, interaction, human perception of a person are an important factor in the process of entering into interaction. Therefore, the application of both treatment compositions in practice helps to improve the effectiveness of management.

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